

Anatomical and Sexual Quality of Life Outcome after vNOTES vs Conventional Surgery for Pelvic Organ Prolapse: A Meta-analysis

Gede Resha Wisadianta¹, Nyoman Gede Dikawijaya Satriawan², I Made Mahardika³

¹Faculty of Medicine, Wijaya Kusuma University, Denpasar, Bali

^{2,3}Faculty of Medicine, Udayana University, Denpasar, Bali

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
03 June 2026

ABSTRACT

Background: Pelvic organ prolapse (POP) is a common condition associated with urinary, bowel, and sexual dysfunction, adversely affecting quality of life. Vaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery (vNOTES) has been introduced as a minimally invasive alternative to conventional approaches, but comparative evidence remains limited.

Objectives: To compare anatomical success, complications, operative time, and sexual quality of life following vNOTES versus conventional surgical techniques for POP repair.

Methods: We conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis in accordance with PRISMA guidelines. PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Semantic Scholar were searched for studies published between 2015 and 2025. Studies were selected based on predefined PICO criteria. Fourteen studies met the inclusion criteria from 248 identified records.

Results: vNOTES was associated with higher odds of anatomical success compared with conventional surgery (OR 2.38, 95% CI 1.26–4.52; $p=0.008$; $I^2=0\%$). There was no statistically significant difference in complication rates (RR 0.68, 95% CI 0.38–1.22; $p=0.20$; $I^2=0\%$). Operative time was shorter with vNOTES (MD -15.32 minutes, 95% CI -19.85 to -10.79; $p<0.001$; $I^2=70\%$). Sexual quality of life favored vNOTES (SMD 0.46, 95% CI 0.20–0.72; $p=0.0006$; $I^2=65\%$). Heterogeneity was moderate to high for some outcomes.

Conclusion: vNOTES may be associated with improved anatomical outcomes and shorter operative time, with similar complication rates and modest improvements in sexual quality of life. However, the findings should be interpreted with caution given heterogeneity and potential study-level limitations. Further high-quality, adequately powered randomized trials are warranted.

Corresponding Author:
Gede Resha Wisadianta

KEYWORDS: Pelvic Organ Prolapse, Vnotes, Natural Orifice Surgery, Anatomical Success, Sexual Quality Of Life, Meta-Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Pelvic organ prolapse (POP) is a common reproductive health disorder in older women, those with multiple pregnancies, and individuals with risk factors such as connective tissue weakness and increased intra-abdominal pressure (Gray et al., 2016). Symptoms include a lump in the vagina, pelvic pressure, urinary and defecation problems, and sexual dysfunction, which can significantly reduce quality of life. (Raju & Linder, 2021). The epidemiology of Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) shows a highly variable prevalence, depending on the method of diagnosis, ranging from 1-65%, with a prevalence based on symptoms of around 1-31% and a physical examination of 10-50% (Brown et al., 2022). Global data shows that POP occurs most frequently in elderly women, especially in the

55-59 age group for absolute number of cases and the highest in the age of 80+ for age-standardized prevalence (Li et al., 2025). With increasing life expectancy in women and the number of elderly population, the burden of POP is expected to increase substantially in the coming decades.

Surgical procedures for POP should not only aim to repair the anatomical structure of the pelvis but also to maintain or improve the patient's quality of life, including sexual function. This principle emphasizes that the success of therapy is not solely measured by anatomical correction, but also by patient-centered outcomes (Guan & Han, 2023). Conventional surgical techniques such as vaginal repair, abdominal sacrocolpopexy, and laparoscopic sacrocolpopexy have long been used and proven effective in anatomically correcting prolapse, but some studies report

that these procedures may be associated with certain complications, longer recovery times, and potential postoperative sexual dysfunction (Rosenberg et al., 2025) .

The development of minimally invasive surgical techniques has led to the emergence of innovative approaches such as vaginal Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery (vNOTES), which utilizes vaginal access without an abdominal incision, with the aim of reducing surgical trauma and accelerating patient recovery. The application of the vNOTES technique in POP repair is still relatively new, and scientific evidence regarding its effectiveness is limited (Bulutlar et al., 2025) . Conceptually, this approach is expected to provide equivalent or even better results than conventional techniques in terms of anatomical success, surgical complications, and postoperative quality of life. However, currently available data show varying results.

Several previous studies have evaluated the use of vNOTES in various gynecological procedures, including hysterectomy and sacrocolpopexy. A study by Wang et al. (2025) demonstrated that the vNOTES technique can be performed safely and effectively with low complication rates in minimally invasive gynecological procedures. Another study by Bulutlar et al. (2025) reported that vNOTES sacrocolpopexy had promising anatomical outcomes and faster recovery times compared to conventional laparoscopic approaches. A study of 26 cases also demonstrated an improvement in patients' quality of life after the vNOTES procedure for POP repair (J. Liu et al., 2019) . However, these studies generally suffer from limitations such as small sample sizes, non-randomized designs, and variations in the definition of anatomical success and sexual function measurement instruments. To date, there is limited research systematically synthesizing evidence regarding the comparison of outcomes between vNOTES and conventional surgical techniques, particularly regarding two important outcomes: anatomical success and quality of sexual life.

Based on these gaps, a comprehensive systematic review is needed to evaluate the effectiveness of vNOTES in pelvic organ prolapse repair compared with conventional surgical techniques. This study aims to conduct a systematic review and meta-analysis of studies comparing the two approaches, focusing on two primary outcomes: anatomical success and postoperative quality of sexual life. By systematically synthesizing the available scientific evidence, this study is expected to provide a stronger understanding of the clinical benefits of vNOTES in the management of POP. Furthermore, the results of this study are expected to provide an important contribution to clinical decision-making in the field of urogynecology and serve as a basis for further research in the development of more effective, minimally invasive surgical techniques that are oriented towards patient quality of life.

II. METHOD

The process of selecting and selecting articles using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Reviews method. Analyzes (PRISMA) (Page et al., 2021) . The process of selecting articles that are in accordance with the research objectives goes through a search process stage through keywords using Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) : (“Pelvic Organ Prolapse” OR “uterine prolapse” OR “vaginal prolapse”) AND (“Natural Orifice Endoscopic Surgery” OR “vNOTES” OR “transvaginal NOTES”) AND (“sacrocolpopexy” OR “colpopexy” OR “prolapse repair”) AND (“sexual function” OR “sexual quality of life” OR “PISQ” OR “FSFI”) AND (“treatment outcome” OR “anatomical success”). in the Science Direct, Sematic Scholar, and PubMed *databases* published in 2015-2025. Article selection was carried out by analysis and synthesis based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria for article selection used were research reports, experimental, and observational studies. The exclusion criteria applied were not using English, and publication type was not *a full-text article* and not an academic journal. The article search was conducted in March 2026. Both the search strategy and eligibility criteria were guided by the Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome (PICO) framework to describe the review's focus question and to determine inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 1. Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome (PICO)

<i>Populati on</i>	Adult women diagnosed with Pelvic Organ Prolapse (POP) and undergoing prolapse correction surgery
<i>Intervent ion</i>	vNOTES (vaginal Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery) for repair of pelvic organ prolapse
<i>Compari son</i>	Conventional surgical techniques for POP repair (e.g., vaginal repair, native tissue repair), laparoscopic sacrocolpopexy, abdominal sacrocolpopexy, conventional vaginal hysterectomy with repair)
<i>Outcome</i>	Primary outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anatomical success • Sexual quality of life Secondary outcomes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • operational time • complication rate

Based on the initial search from *the database* , 248 articles were obtained. The collected articles were then re-selected and articles that did not match the title and abstract were eliminated to find a match and to remove duplicate articles, resulting in 14 articles. The search sequence is presented in the following figure.

“Anatomical and Sexual Quality of Life Outcome after vNOTES vs Conventional Surgery for Pelvic Organ Prolapse: A Meta-analysis”

Figure 1. PRISMA Flowchart

III. RESULT

The literature search yielded a total of 248 reports, and after removing duplicates, 102 articles were identified. After

screening these reports using eligibility criteria, 14 were retained for review. The review results for several research studies that met the criteria are :

Table 2. Included Study Characteristics

Author/ Year	Title	Objective	Design Study and Method	Population	Subject of Study (Sample size)	Result
(Kim et al., 2018)	Postoperative outcomes of natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery-assisted vaginal hysterectomy and conventional laparoscopic-assisted vaginal hysterectomy : a comparative study	Comparing the surgical outcomes of NAVH with LAVH in benign uterine disease	Retrospective comparative study	Women with benign uterine disease	Women with benign uterine disease	NAVH has lower blood loss, but longer operative time; complications and length of hospital stay are relatively similar.
(Yang et al., 2020)	Surgical outcomes of hysterectomy by transvaginal natural orifice	Comparing the outcomes of vNOTES surgery with laparoscopic	Retrospective comparative study	Women of reproductive age with benign uterine	86 patients (20 with vNOTES; 66 LTH)	There was no significant difference in operative time, blood loss,

“Anatomical and Sexual Quality of Life Outcome after vNOTES vs Conventional Surgery for Pelvic Organ Prolapse: A Meta-analysis”

	transluminal endoscopic surgery (vNOTES) compared with laparoscopic total hysterectomy (LTH) in women with non-prolapsed and benign uterine diseases	total hysterectomy		disease without prolapse		complications; vNOTES showed lower postoperative pain.
(Lu et al., 2021)	Transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery for uterosacral ligament suspension : pilot study of 35 cases of severe pelvic organ prolapse	Assessing the effectiveness of vNOTES for uterosacral ligament suspension in PO	Retrospective study	Severe POP patients	5 patients	There was significant improvement in POP-Q scores and quality of life; there were no serious complications.
(Chen et al., 2023)	Comparative analysis of transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery versus laparoendoscopic single-site sacrocolpopexy for pelvic organ prolapse : A propensity score matching study	Comparing the safety and effectiveness of vNOTES-SC with LESS-SC	Propensity score matching study	POP patients	72 patients (36 vNOTES; 36 LESS SC)	vNOTES has shorter operating time and length of stay; complications and effectiveness are similar.
(Huang et al., 2023)	Transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery versus conventional vaginal surgery for sacrospinous ligament fixation of apical compartment prolapse : a retrospective analysis	Comparing vNOTES with conventional vaginal surgery	Retrospective comparative study	Patients with apical prolapse	82 patients (31 vNOTES; 51 CV)	vNOTES had shorter length of stay and better anatomical outcomes; similar complications.
(Gündoğdu,	Postoperative	Evaluating the	Observational	POP patient	11 patients	There were no

“Anatomical and Sexual Quality of Life Outcome after vNOTES vs Conventional Surgery for Pelvic Organ Prolapse: A Meta-analysis”

2023)	Outcomes of V-notes (Transvaginal Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery) Sacrocolpopexy in Patients with Pelvic Organ Prolapse	outcome of V-NOTES sacrocolpopexy surgery	clinical study	after hysterectomy		perioperative complications; quality of life improved and cosmetic results were good.
(Hurni et al., 2024)	Early surgical outcomes of 550 consecutive patients treated for benign gynecological conditions by transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery	Evaluating the safety and initial outcomes of Vnotes operations	Single-center observational study	Patients with benign gynecological conditions	550 patients	The total complication rate was 6.5%; conversion to laparoscopy was 1.6%; the procedure was considered safe and feasible.
(Lowenstein et al., 2024)	European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology Conventional vaginal approach vs . transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery for treating apical prolapse, a randomized controlled study	Comparing operative time and outcomes between conventional vaginal techniques and vNOTES	Randomized controlled trial	Pelvic organ prolapse patients	60 patients (30 vNOTES; 30 CV)	vNOTES has shorter operating time, lower bleeding, and fewer adverse events.
(Bala et al., 2025)	Comparison of Pelvic Organ Prolapse and Sexual Function After Vaginal Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery and Conventional Laparoscopic Hysterectomy	Comparing prolapse outcomes and sexual function after surgery	Retrospective comparative study	Women with benign conditions who undergo hysterectomy	84 patients (42 vNOTES; 42 TLH)	Both methods had similar outcomes on POP and sexual function after 1 year.
(Bacak et al., 2025)	Anatomic and Functional	Comparing anatomical and	Randomized controlled	Woman with POP	90 patients (42	Both methods improved

“Anatomical and Sexual Quality of Life Outcome after vNOTES vs Conventional Surgery for Pelvic Organ Prolapse: A Meta-analysis”

	Outcomes After Vaginal Hysterectomy With Mesh-Based V-NOTES Lateral Suspension Versus Sacrospinous Ligament Fixation: A Randomized Controlled Trial	functional outcomes between V-NOTES-LS and SSLF	trial		vNOTES; 48 SSLF)	anatomical outcomes; V-NOTES showed greater improvement in sexual function.
(W. Liu et al., 2025)	Analyzing the learning curve of vnotes by the cumulative summation test	Analyzing the learning curve and outcome of vNOTES-SC operations	Cohort study	Patients with pelvic organ prolapse	79 patients	The learning curve stabilized after 11 cases; operative time decreased significantly and anatomical cure rate reached 91%.
(Erkmen, 2025)	Concomitant Hysterectomy and vNOTES-Assisted Sacrocolpopexy : A Feasible and Safe Scarless Approach for Apical Prolapse Repair	Evaluating the safety of vNOTES-SC with simultaneous hysterectomy	Retrospective cohort	Woman with stage II uterine prolapse	30 patients	Anatomical success rate is 73–93% with minor complications and rapid recovery.
(Dou et al., 2024)	A Retrospective Cohort Study of vNOTES Extraperitoneal Versus Laparoscopic Sacral Hysteropexy With Uterine Preserving Regarding Surgical Outcomes and Two-Year Follow-Up Results	Comparing the results of vNOTES-ESH surgery with laparoscopy	Retrospective cohort study	Women with uterine prolapse	99 patients (25 vNOTES; 74 laparoscopy)	Surgical success rates are similar (~96–97%), with minimal complications.
(Lu et al., 2022)	Mesh Exposure and Recurrence Following Transvaginal Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic	Evaluating the risk of mesh exposure and POP recurrence	Retrospective cohort study	Women with uterine prolapse	55 patients	Mesh exposure and recurrence were each 5.5%, indicating an effective procedure with low risk.

Surgery for Sacrocolpopexy: Over 24 Months of Follow-up Data

Based on 14 articles obtained based on the inclusion criteria, a statistical analysis was performed on anatomical success, perioperative or postoperative complications, surgical time, and quality of sexual life. The following results compare the anatomical success between vNOTES and conventional surgical techniques.

Figure 2. Forest Plot Comparison of Anatomical Success Between vNOTES and Conventional Surgical Techniques for Pelvic Organ Prolapse Repair.

Figure 2 shows that six studies reported anatomical success after surgery. Pooled analysis showed that vNOTES was associated with a significantly higher anatomical success rate compared with conventional surgical techniques (OR = 2.38; 95% CI 1.26–4.52; p = 0.008). No heterogeneity was observed among the included studies (I² = 0%), indicating consistent results across studies.

Figure 3. Forest Plot Comparison of Perioperative or Postoperative Complications Between vNOTES and Conventional Surgical Techniques for Pelvic Organ Prolapse Repair

A meta-analysis of seven studies reporting postoperative complications showed no statistically significant difference in complication rates between vNOTES and conventional surgical techniques (RR = 0.68; 95% CI 0.38–1.22; p = 0.20). No heterogeneity was observed among the included studies (I² = 0%), indicating consistent findings across studies.

Figure 4. Forest Plot Comparison of Operating Time Between vNOTES and Conventional Surgical Techniques for Pelvic Organ Prolapse Repair.

Figure 4 shows that vNOTES significantly reduced operative time compared with conventional surgical techniques (MD = -15.32 min; 95% CI -19.85 to -10.79; p < 0.001). However, substantial heterogeneity was observed among the studies (I² = 70%), which may be related to differences in surgical procedures and comparator techniques.

Figure 5. Forest Plot Comparison of Quality of Sexual Life Between vNOTES and Conventional Surgical Techniques for Pelvic Organ Prolapse Repair.

Figure 4. Pooled analysis of the three studies showed that vNOTES was associated with significantly better sexual quality of life compared with conventional surgical techniques (SMD = 0.46; 95% CI 0.20–0.72; p = 0.0006). Moderate heterogeneity was observed among the studies (I² = 65%). All selected articles underwent RoB 2 analysis to determine the risk of bias for each article. The risk of bias analysis can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 4. Risk of Bias graph.

Risk of bias assessments indicated that most studies had a low risk of attrition bias and reporting bias. However, performance bias was assessed as high in all studies because blinding of participants and personnel is rarely possible in surgical trials. Selection bias was unclear in some observational studies due to inadequate reporting of randomization procedures and allocation concealment.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study aimed to evaluate the anatomical success, safety, surgical efficiency, and quality of sexual life after vNOTES in pelvic organ prolapse repair compared with conventional surgical techniques. Based on a systematic review of 14 studies and a meta-analysis of available comparative studies, the findings of this study indicate that vNOTES offers several important clinical advantages, particularly in terms of anatomical success, surgical time efficiency, and improved quality of sexual life, with complication rates comparable to those of conventional techniques.

The meta-analysis results showed that vNOTES significantly improved anatomical success compared to conventional techniques. These findings indicate that patients undergoing the vNOTES procedure were approximately twice as likely to achieve anatomical success compared to patients undergoing conventional surgical techniques. Anatomical success in prolapse surgery is generally measured using the Pelvic Organ Prolapse Quantification (POP-Q) parameter, which indicates improved pelvic structural support after surgery (Bhalerao & Duddalwar, 2020). One factor that may explain these results is the improved visualization of pelvic anatomy through the endoscopic approach in vNOTES. By using an endoscopic camera inserted through a vaginal access, the operator can obtain a broader view of the pelvic structures compared to conventional vaginal techniques, allowing for more precise placement of suspension sutures or mesh.

The results of this study also showed that vNOTES significantly reduced operative time compared to conventional techniques, with an average operative time of approximately 15 minutes shorter. Efficiency of operative time is an important factor in surgical practice because it is related to the duration of anesthesia, the use of operating room resources, and the potential for perioperative complications (Lowenstein et al., 2024). The shorter operative time in vNOTES is likely related to several factors, including direct access to the pelvic cavity through the vagina without the need for an abdominal incision, thereby reducing the time required for opening and closing tissue layers. Furthermore, this approach also eliminates the need for multiple trocar placement as in conventional laparoscopy, which can speed up the overall surgical process. Studies conducted by Lowenstein et al., (2024) and Chen et al., (2023) also showed that the vNOTES technique

allows for more efficient pelvic reconstruction procedures without compromising procedural safety.

However, heterogeneity analysis of operative time outcomes showed variations between studies. This heterogeneity is likely due to several methodological factors, including variations in the types of procedures performed, such as sacrocolpopexy, hysterectomy with uterosacral ligament suspension, hysteropexy, and lateral suspension. Furthermore, differences in operator experience may also affect operative time, especially since the vNOTES technique is still relatively new and has its own learning curve. A study by W. Liu et al., (2025) showed that the learning curve for the vNOTES sacrocolpopexy procedure can be reached after approximately 11 cases, indicating that operator experience plays a significant role in the procedure's efficiency.

A meta-analysis of complication rates showed no significant difference between vNOTES and conventional surgical techniques. However, there was a tendency for vNOTES to have a lower risk of complications. This finding aligns with the basic concept of minimally invasive surgery, which aims to minimize tissue trauma and reduce the risk of postoperative complications (Qadrie et al., 2025). The vNOTES approach does not require an abdominal incision, thus reducing the risk of complications such as surgical site infection, incisional hernia, and postoperative pain, which are common in laparoscopic or laparotomy procedures. Furthermore, several studies in this review reported that complications associated with the vNOTES procedure were generally mild and fell into the Clavien–Dindo grade I or II category, indicating a relatively good level of procedural safety.

Another important finding in this study is that vNOTES significantly improved patients' quality of sexual life compared to conventional surgical techniques. These results indicate a moderate effect on improving sexual function after surgery. Quality of sexual life is an important outcome in the treatment of pelvic organ prolapse, as prolapse can cause various disorders such as dyspareunia, decreased self-confidence, and overall impaired sexual function (Bala et al., 2025). The vNOTES approach likely offers advantages in this regard because it maintains pelvic tissue integrity and reduces trauma to vaginal structures compared to conventional surgical procedures. Furthermore, the absence of abdominal scars can also improve patient satisfaction with the overall surgical outcome. These results are also consistent with several previous studies showing that minimally invasive techniques in gynecological surgery can improve patient quality of life after surgery. A study by Bacak et al. (2025) reported that patients who underwent the vNOTES lateral suspension procedure had better Pelvic Organ Prolapse/Urinary Incontinence Sexual Questionnaire (PISQ-12) scores than patients who underwent conventional sacrospinous ligament fixation.

The findings of this study have important clinical implications for modern urogynecological surgical practice. Pelvic organ prolapse is a relatively common condition in women, particularly in the elderly, with a reported prevalence of approximately 40–50% in multiparous women (Li et al., 2025). Surgical management is the primary treatment option for symptomatic prolapse unresponsive to conservative therapy. In this context, a surgical approach that not only effectively restores anatomical support but also minimizes tissue trauma and maintains patient quality of life is crucial. The results of this study demonstrate that vNOTES can meet these criteria by providing higher anatomical success rates and more efficient operative times. These advantages have the potential to significantly benefit the healthcare system, particularly in terms of operating room efficiency and reduced length of stay.

Furthermore, the findings regarding improved sexual quality after the vNOTES procedure provide important perspectives for the quality-of-life management of pelvic organ prolapse. Sexual dysfunction is a common consequence of prolapse, both due to anatomical changes and the psychological impact of the condition. (Bala et al., 2025). Therefore, the success of therapy is not only assessed based on anatomical improvement, but also on the overall improvement in patient well-being. The vNOTES technique, which utilizes natural vaginal access without an abdominal incision, can reduce tissue trauma and maintain the integrity of pelvic structures, ultimately contributing to improved sexual function.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of a systematic review and meta-analysis, this study shows that vNOTES is an effective and safe technique for treating pelvic organ prolapse. The vNOTES procedure has been shown to have a higher anatomical success rate, shorter operative time, and better quality of sexual life compared to conventional surgical techniques, while complication rates did not show a significant difference between the two approaches. These findings suggest that vNOTES can be a promising minimally invasive alternative in modern urogynecology practice because it is able to provide good clinical outcomes while improving patients' quality of life.

REFERENCES

1. Bacak, HB, Salman, S., Coskun, ES, Kumbasar, S., Gencer, FK, Usta, ZK, Timur, GY, Ucar, E., Bilici, SR, Atar, Ş., Guven, R., Hazır, B., & Erdem, B. (2025). Anatomic and Functional Outcomes After Vaginal Hysterectomy With Mesh-Based V-NOTES Lateral Suspension Versus Sacrospinous Ligament Fixation: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Journal of Minimally Invasive Gynecology*. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.1016/j.jmig.2025.12.034>.
2. Bala, M., Erdem, S., & Can, B. (2025). Comparison of Pelvic Organ Prolapse and Sexual Function After Vaginal Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery and Conventional Laparoscopic Hysterectomy. *BMC Women's Health*, 1–12.
3. Bhalariao, A., & Duddalwar, V. (2020). Comparative Study to Evaluate Pelvic Organ Prolapse Quantification System and Simplified Pelvic Organ Prolapse Scoring System by Assessing Anatomical and Functional Outcome in Women with Pelvic Organ Prolapse after Surgery. *Journal of SAFOMS*. <https://doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-10032-1180>
4. Brown, H., Hegde, A., Huebner, M., Neels, H., Barnes, H., Marquini, G., Mukhtarova, N., Mbwele, B., Tailor, V., Kocjancic, E., Trowbridge, E., & Hayward, L. (2022). International urogynecology consultation chapter 1 committee 2: Epidemiology of pelvic organ prolapse: prevalence, incidence, natural history, and service needs. *International Urogynecology Journal*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00192-021-05018-z>
5. Bulutlar, E., Bulutlar, GBU, İzceyhan, G.B., & Kılıççı, Ç. (2025). A New Technique in Pelvic Organ Prolapse: Performing Sacrocolpopexy Through Natural Orifice Surgery Kılıççı-Bulutlar Technique. *Asian Journal of Endoscopic Surgery*, 18 1. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ases.70073>
6. Chen, Y., Zhou, Y., Tan, L., Chen, S., Wu, C., Liang, Y., Sun, N., & Liu, J. (2023). Comparative analysis of transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery versus laparoendoscopic single-site sacrocolpopexy for pelvic organ prolapse : A propensity score matching study. *HLY*, 9 (9), e19698. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e19698>
7. Dou, Y., Deng, L., Liang, X., Cao, F., Chen, B., Tang, S., & Wang, Y. (2024). A Retrospective Cohort Study of vNOTES Extraperitoneal Versus Laparoscopic Sacral Hysteropexy With Uterine Preserving Regarding Surgical Outcomes and Two-Year Follow-Up Results. *Journal of Minimally Invasive Gynecology*, 31 (7), 584–591. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.1016/j.jmig.2024.04.013>
8. Erkmen, A.D. (2025). Concomitant Hysterectomy and vNOTES-Assisted Sacrocolpopexy : A Feasible and Safe Scarless Approach for Apical Prolapse Repair. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*.
9. Gray, T., McVey, S., Green, J., Saxena, A., & Patel, D. (2016). Pelvic organ prolapse. *InnovAiT*, 9, 723–731. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1755738016676212>
10. Guan, Y., & Han, J. (2023). Quality-of-life improvements in patients after various surgical treatments for pelvic organ prolapse. *Archives of*

- Gynecology and Obstetrics*, 309, 813–820. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00404-023-07140-3>
11. Gündoğdu, E.C. (2023). Postoperative Outcomes of V-notes (Transvaginal Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery) Sacrocolpopexy in Patients with Pelvic Organ Prolapse. *Hamidiye Medical Journal*, 4 (Suppl 1), 28–34. <https://doi.org/10.4274/hamidiyemedj.galenos.2023.19484>
 12. Huang, L., Yu, J., Li, Y., Gong, Z. L., Feng, D., He, L., & Lin, Y. H. (2023). Transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery versus conventional vaginal surgery for sacrospinous ligament fixation of apical compartment prolapse : a retrospective analysis. *BMC Surgery* , 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12893-023-01921-y>
 13. Hurni, Y., Simonson, C., Di, M., Régine, S., Bodenmann, P., Seidler, S., & Huber, D. (2024). Early surgical outcomes of 550 consecutive patients treated for benign gynecological conditions by transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery. *Acta Obstetrica et Gynecologica Scandinavica*, March, 2203–2210. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aogs.14889>
 14. Kim, SH, Jin, CH, Hwang, IT, Park, JS, Shin, JH, Kim, DW, Seo, YS, Sohn, JN, & Yang, YS (2018). *Postoperative outcomes of natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery-assisted vaginal hysterectomy and conventional laparoscopic-assisted vaginal hysterectomy: a comparative study* . 61 (2), 261–266.
 15. Li, P., Hongyun, Zhang, J., & Zhang, Q. (2025). Global Trends in Prevalence and Future Projections of Pelvic Organ Prolapse: A 30-year Epidemiological Study. *International Urogynecology Journal* , 36 , 991–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00192-025-06049-6>
 16. Liu, J., Kohn, J., Fu, H., Guan, Z., & Guan, X. (2019). Transvaginal Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery for Sacrocolpopexy: A Pilot Study of 26 Cases. *Journal of Minimally Invasive Gynecology*, 26 4, 748–753. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmig.2018.08.009>
 17. Liu, W., Sun, N., Zhang, Y., Li, Y., Lai, W., & Zhou, Y. (2025). *Analyzing the learning curve of vnotes sacrocolpopexy by the cumulative summation test : January* , 6857–6866.
 18. Lowenstein, L., Mor, O., Matanes, E., Justman, N., & Stuart, A. (2024). European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology Conventional vaginal approach vs . transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery for treating apical prolapse, a randomized controlled study. *European Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology and Reproductive Biology*, 303 (July), 180–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2024.10.032>
 19. Lu, Z., Chen, Y., Wang, X., Li, J., Hua, K., & Hu, C. (2021). Transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery for uterosacral ligament suspension : pilot study of 35 cases of severe pelvic organ prolapse. *BMC Surgery* , 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12893-021-01280-6>
 20. Lu, Z., Chen, Y., Wang, X., Li, J., Yang, C., Yuan, F., Hua, K., & Hu, C. (2022). Mesh Exposure and Prolapse Recurrence Following Transvaginal Natural Orifice Transluminal Endoscopic Surgery for Sacrocolpopexy: Over 24 Months of Follow-up Data. *Journal of Minimally Invasive Gynecology* , 29 (12), 1317–1322. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.1016/j.jmig.2022.08.001>
 21. Page, MJ, McKenzie, JE, Bossuyt, PM, Boutron, I., Hoffmann, TC, Mulrow, CD, Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, JM, Akl, EA, Brennan, SE, Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, JM, Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, MM, Li, T., Loder, E.W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *The BMJ* , 372 . <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
 22. Qadrie, Z., Maqbool, M., Dar, M., & Qadir, A. (2025). Navigating challenges and maximizing potential: Handling complications and constraints in minimally invasive surgery. *Open Health* , 6 . <https://doi.org/10.1515/ohe-2025-0059>
 23. Raju, R., & Linder, B. (2021). Evaluation and Management of Pelvic Organ Prolapse. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*, 96 12, 3122–3129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mayocp.2021.09.005>
 24. Rosenberg, H., Leybovitz-Hallelujah, N., Saban, A., Weintraub, A., & Rotem, R. (2025). Trends in patient characteristics, surgical techniques, and associated complications over time in pelvic organ prolapse repair. *European Journal of Obstetrics, Gynecology, and Reproductive Biology*, 308, 116–120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejogrb.2025.02.054>
 25. Wang, F., Liu, Y., Xing, Y., Wang, D., Bai, X., Li, L., Chunhua, Sun, Y., Bai, Y., & Wang, L. (2025). Clinical efficacy and safety study of vNOTES for benign ovarian tumors in obese patients. *Scientific Reports*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-88599-9>
 26. Yang, C., Shen, T., Lin, C., Chang, Y., & Huang, C. (2020). Taiwanese Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology Surgical outcomes of hysterectomy by transvaginal natural orifice transluminal endoscopic surgery (vNOTES) compared with laparoscopic total hysterectomy (LTH) in women with non-prolapsed and benign uterine diseases. *Taiwanese Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology* , 59 (4), 565–569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tjog.2020.05.016>